

DEVELOPMENT OF SELF-MOTIVATION TO LEARN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS

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Distance learning presents unique challenges for students, and maintaining a high level of self-motivation in learning a foreign language becomes even more crucial. The relevance of developing self-motivation in studying a foreign language among medical university students during distance and blended learning is influenced by several factors:

- *Globalization and international communication:* Modern medicine is a global discipline, and medical professionals often encounter the need to communicate with colleagues, patients, and researchers from different countries. Knowledge of foreign languages becomes a key element of effective professional communication.
- *Intercultural interaction:* Students in medical universities may interact with patients and colleagues from diverse cultures, languages, and ethnic groups. Understanding a foreign language and cultural peculiarities enhances effective interactions and improves the quality of medical care.
- *Advancement of scientific knowledge:* Medical science is continuously evolving, and numerous research papers and publications are conducted in English and other foreign languages. Students who are proficient in a foreign language have greater access to the latest scientific discoveries and international medical journals.
- *Personal and professional development:* Learning a foreign language fosters cognitive skills, elevates educational levels, and broadens the horizons of students. It also enhances their competitiveness in the job market and opens up new opportunities for career growth [2, 3].

Developing self-motivation to learn a foreign language is a valuable skill that not only facilitates effective language acquisition but also holds long-term significance for the personal and professional growth of medical university students. Here are some practical tips for medical university students to cultivate self-motivation and enhance the effectiveness of learning a foreign language in a distance learning environment:

- a) **Set clear goals:** Define specific and achievable language learning objectives. Break them down into sub-goals and establish timelines for accomplishing each one. This will help you navigate the learning process and foster a positive attitude towards achieving success.
- b) **Use motivational methods:** Find techniques that inspire you in language learning. It could be rewarding yourself for achieving small milestones, visualizing success, seeking support from family and friends, or engaging with those who are more proficient in the language.
- c) **Create a stimulating environment:** Surround yourself with helpful language materials such as books, articles, movies, and music in the target language. Get a language partner or join online language groups to engage in conversations and practice the foreign language.
- d) **Plan your study process:** Develop a schedule for language learning and stick to it rigorously. Allocate time to different language aspects such as reading, writing, listening, and speaking. Consistent practice of the foreign language will reinforce skills and maintain interest in learning.
- e) **Collaborate with fellow students:** Find friends or classmates with whom you can study and practice the foreign language together. Sharing experiences and knowledge will enhance your understanding of the material and foster mutual motivation.
- f) **Evaluate your progress:** Regularly track your language learning progress. Assess your achievements and celebrate successes. Steady improvement in language proficiency will serve as a powerful motivator for further development.

- g) Overcome challenges: Learning a foreign language can be challenging, but do not be disheartened by difficulties. Embrace them as a natural part of the learning process and strive to overcome them. Confidence in your abilities will help you surmount obstacles on the path to success.
- h) Leverage technology: Utilize available language learning apps, online courses, and resources that will aid in structuring your language learning journey and provide additional opportunities for practice.
- i) Stay positive: Positive thinking and self-confidence play a significant role in maintaining a high level of self-motivation. Remember to reward yourself for every step towards success and not to fret over possible setbacks [4, 5].

In conclusion, developing self-motivation in learning a foreign language is essential for medical university students, particularly in the context of distance learning. It is a valuable skill that not only facilitates effective language acquisition but also contributes to the personal and professional growth of students, making them more competent and self-assured medical professionals in the globalized world.

References

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